

MULTI-SCALE IDENTIFICATION USING M-CRE BASED ON FULL-FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Shaojuan Huang, Pierre Feissel and Pierre Villon
Laboratoire Roberval, CNRS UMR 7337, Université de Technologie de Compiègne
Rue du Docteur Schweitzer CS 60319, 60203 Compiègne, France
shaojuan.huang@utc.fr, pierre.feissel@utc.fr, pierre.villon@utc.fr

Keywords: Full field measurement, Identification, Inverse approach, Modified constitutive relation error, Multi-scale

ABSTRACT

For the identification of the mechanical behavior of composite with large RVE (such as 3D composite), the full-field measurements can offer a very rich information. Some specific identification strategies have been proposed, but most of these methods consider the identification problem only on the measured area and would usually need boundary conditions to be performed. However, the boundary conditions are not always completely known and might not be on the measurement zone. There is hence a need of identification methods allowing both the identification over the whole specimen and the dealing of missing boundary conditions. The modified constitutive relation error (M-CRE) allows dealing with such situations through the taking into account of the whole available information from a theoretical and experimental point of view. Furthermore, the lack of information outside the measurement zone leads us to propose a two-scale approach where heterogeneous properties are sought at the measurement level and homogeneous ones at the specimen level.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the middle 20th century, experimental methods in solid mechanics focused on point-wise measurements for quantitative data. It means that specimen response is characterized only globally. Since without information between measurement points, the measured response represent an averaged overall material response. In this case, only the homogeneous material undergoing uniform deformation can be measured the true material behaviour. In the late 20th century, the development of full field measurements, a field record of a quantity (displacement, deformation, density, temperature), can offer a rich information allowing to take into consideration heterogeneous tests in terms of stress for the characterization of material behaviour. The source of heterogeneity of the test can come from the material itself, the geometry of the specimen or the loading. At the same time, the rapid growth of computer technology that spurred continued growth of computational methods also provided the foundation for the explosion of growth in vision-based full-field experimental measurement method. Digital image correlation (DIC), which appeared in the early 1980s [1][2], is one of the new vision-based full-field measurement. In this scheme, a video camera observes an object and the image is digitized and sent to a computer. Within the computer, numerical schemes utilize the basic theory of deformation as a mapping [3].

A key point is then to develop or adapt identification strategies based on DIC measurements. Some specific methods have been proposed in the past years and a review can be found in [4]. Most of these methods consider the identification problem only on the measured area and would usually need boundary conditions to be performed. For example, finite element model updating (FEMU) is aimed at the identification of constitutive parameters by minimizing the discrepancy, between a measured quantity, such as displacement, strains or forces, and its prediction by the model for some assumed values of parameters [5]. On one hand, we can exploit any information which is supplementary relative to boundary conditions for ensuring the well-posedness of a forward problem with known material properties. On the other hand, sometime the simultaneous knowledge of forces and displacements over some part of the sample under examination is the data overdetermined. We need to make a hard choice of variant (cost functions focusing on either kinematic fields or forces) depend on the precise nature of the available data.

To improve the effectiveness of the overdetermined data, constitutive relation error (CRE) is applicable to any identification problem for which overdetermined data are available. CRE is an energy measure of the discrepancy between a stress field given a priori and another stress field evaluated from a given displacement field using a constitutive model [6]. For a constitutive parameter identification problem for which overdetermined data are used, it is possible to modify the definitions of the admissible field spaces in order to include all the available experimental information.

However, the boundary condition are not always completely known. Even if they are known (e.g. free edge), they might not be on the boundary of the measurement zone. There is hence a need of identification method allowing

both the identification over the whole specimen, and the dealing of missing boundary condition. **The modified constitutive relation error (M-CRE)** [7] as proposed here is a good method to identify static elastic properties, which allows to deal with such situations through the taking into account of the whole available information from a theoretical and experimental point of view [8]. Furthermore, it appeared to be robust with respect to the measurements perturbations in previous studies.

In the usual experiment cases, the measurement zone is only a sub-part of the specimen. If we use the mono-scale approach, we can only identify the local heterogeneous properties of the measurement zone. It means that the lack of information outside the measurement zone prevents from identifying heterogeneous properties in this area. Hence, a multi-scale approach is proposed to account for any specimen where micro heterogeneous properties are sought at the measurement level and macros homogeneous ones at the specimen level.

In Section 2 of this paper, we present the identification framework and describe the various identification strategies with different kinds of boundary conditions on mono-scale. The details of trade-off and combination of the information between different scales are described in Section 3. We apply the M-CRE method on some numerical examples in Section 4, and the results confirm its effectiveness and robustness.

2. MONO-SCALE IDENTIFICATION STRATEGY

2.1 Framework: direct problem and measurements

The identification framework is the one of a mechanical test on a specimen Ω where the force is measured over $\partial_f\Omega$ as well as the displacement field on one part of the specimen surface Ω_m (Figure 1). We can also assume a part of the edge of the specimen is free of load $\partial_d\Omega$ et $\partial_\theta\Omega$. The elastic properties of the specimen collected in the vector $\underline{\theta}$ can be sought as homogeneous or heterogeneous, isotropic or not. This can lead to the following model and equations describing the available information, both experimental and theoretical. The specimen is hence assumed to be a $2D$ domain Ω , in plane stress. The equations verified by the stress $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}$, the displacement \underline{u} and the parameter $\underline{\theta}$ are as follow :

Figure 1 - Mono-scale: direct problem

- On Ω ,
 - Equilibrium: $\text{div } \underline{\underline{\sigma}} = \underline{0}$
 - Constitutive relation: $\underline{\underline{\sigma}} = C(\underline{\theta})\underline{\underline{\epsilon}}$
 - Kinematic compatibility: $\underline{\underline{\epsilon}} = \underline{\nabla}^s \underline{u}$
 - On Ω_m ,
 - Displacement measurement: $\underline{u} = \underline{\tilde{u}}$
 - On $\partial_d\Omega$,
 - Free edge boundary condition: $\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{n} = \underline{0}$
 - On $\partial_f\Omega$,
 - Measured traction boundary condition: $\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{n} = \underline{f}$
- or,
- Measured global load: $\int_{\partial\Omega_f} \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{n} dS \cdot \underline{N}_0 = F_0$
- On $\partial_\theta\Omega = \partial\Omega \setminus \partial_d\Omega \setminus \partial_f\Omega$, no boundary condition

2.2 Splitting of the equations

The principle of the modified constitutive relation error is to define the mechanical fields (displacement and stress) and material properties that are a trade-off between all the available information [9]. The trade-off is built so that the reliable information should be exactly verified and the less reliable information only verified at best by minimizing a functional. To that purpose, the various equations of the identification problem are split into three groups:

- the group of the reliable equations: the equilibrium equation and the kinematic compatibility on Ω , the free edge assumption on $\partial_d\Omega$;
- the group of the less reliable equations: the constitutive relation on Ω (whose parameters are sought), the equality to the displacement measurements $\tilde{\underline{u}}$ on Ω_m (with some uncertainties);
- the group of equations whose reliability depends on the study case: the boundary condition of the traction distribution or global load on $\partial_f\Omega$. If it needs to restore the balance between strain and displacement, we put this equation into the functional of minimization, but if it needs to provide a better posed basic problem, we put it in constraints.

2.3 The mono-scale identification problem

In order to identify the properties of the material, the triplet $(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}, \underline{\theta})$ is sought as the solution of a minimization problem where the reliable equations are considered as constraints and the less reliable equations are defining a function that is to be minimized. We introduce:

- the space associated with the constraints on displacement:

$$\mathcal{U}_{Ad} = \{\underline{u} \in H^1(\Omega)\} \quad (1)$$

- the space associated with the constraints on stress:

- equilibrium and free edge:

$$\mathcal{S}_{Ad}^0 = \{\underline{\sigma} \in H_{div}(\Omega) / \underline{div} \underline{\sigma} = \underline{0} \text{ sur } \Omega, \underline{\sigma} \cdot \underline{n} = \underline{0} \text{ sur } \partial_d\Omega\} \quad (2)$$

- traction distribution on $\partial_f\Omega$:

$$\mathcal{S}_{Ad}^f = \{\underline{\sigma} \in H_{div}^f(\Omega) / \underline{\sigma} \cdot \underline{n} = \underline{f} \text{ sur } \partial_f\Omega\} \quad (3)$$

- global load on $\partial_f\Omega$:

$$\mathcal{S}_{Ad}^F = \{\underline{\sigma} \in H_{div}^F(\Omega) / \int_{\partial_f\Omega} \underline{\sigma} \cdot \underline{n} dS \cdot \underline{N}_0 = F_0\} \quad (4)$$

- the term of distance to the constitutive relation:

$$\mathcal{J}_1(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{u}, \underline{\theta}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (\underline{\sigma} - C \underline{\xi}(\underline{u})) C^{-1} (\underline{\sigma} - C \underline{\xi}(\underline{u})) d\Omega \quad (5)$$

- the term of the distance to displacement measurements on Ω_m :

$$\mathcal{J}_2(\underline{u}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_m} \|\underline{u} - \tilde{\underline{u}}\|^2 d\Omega_m \quad (6)$$

- the term of the distance to traction distribution on $\partial_f\Omega$:

$$\mathcal{J}_3(\underline{\sigma}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\partial_f\Omega} \|\underline{\sigma} \cdot \underline{n} - \underline{f}\|^2 dS \quad (7)$$

- the term of the distance to global load on $\partial_f\Omega$:

$$\mathcal{J}_4(\underline{\sigma}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_{\partial_f\Omega} \underline{\sigma} \cdot \underline{n} dS \cdot \underline{N}_0 - F_0 \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

Study case	Constraints	Functional
$\partial_f \Omega = \emptyset$	$S_{Ad} = S_{Ad}^0$	$\mathcal{J}(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{u}, \underline{\theta}) = \mathcal{J}_1 + \alpha \mathcal{J}_2$
Traction distribution reliable	$S_{Ad} = S_{Ad}^0 \cap S_{Ad}^f$	$\mathcal{J}(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{u}, \underline{\theta}) = \mathcal{J}_1 + \alpha \mathcal{J}_2$
Traction distribution less reliable	$S_{Ad} = S_{Ad}^0$	$\mathcal{J}(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{u}, \underline{\theta}) = \mathcal{J}_1 + \alpha \mathcal{J}_2 + \beta \mathcal{J}_3$
Global load reliable	$S_{Ad} = S_{Ad}^0 \cap S_{Ad}^f$	$\mathcal{J}(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{u}, \underline{\theta}) = \mathcal{J}_1 + \alpha \mathcal{J}_2$
Global load less reliable	$S_{Ad} = S_{Ad}^0$	$\mathcal{J}(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{u}, \underline{\theta}) = \mathcal{J}_1 + \alpha \mathcal{J}_2 + \beta \mathcal{J}_4$

Table 1 - Various possible formulations (α and β are positive weighting coefficients)

Table 1 presents the various possible formulations which can be used in different cases.

We can conclude the definition of the identification problem as the following:

Find the field $(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}) \in \mathcal{U}_{Ad} \times \mathcal{S}_{Ad}$ and the set of parameters $\underline{\theta}$ minimizing $\mathcal{J}(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}, \underline{\theta})$:

$$\min_{(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}, \underline{\theta}) \in \mathcal{U}_{Ad} \times \mathcal{S}_{Ad} \times \Theta_{Ad}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}, \underline{\theta}) \quad (9)$$

In practice, the minimization is split into a sequential minimization:

$$\min_{\underline{\theta} \in \Theta_{Ad}} \min_{(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}) \in \mathcal{U}_{Ad} \times \mathcal{S}_{Ad}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}, \underline{\theta}) \quad (10)$$

- For a given $\underline{\theta}$, find $(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma})$ minimizing $\mathcal{J}(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}, \underline{\theta})$ under the above constraints:

$$\min_{(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}) \in \mathcal{U}_{Ad} \times \mathcal{S}_{Ad}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}, \underline{\theta}) \quad (11)$$

This defines the basic problem that yields the mechanical fields that are a trade-off between the informations for a given set of material parameters. The solution of the basic problem is noted $(\underline{u}(\underline{\theta}), \underline{\sigma}(\underline{\theta}))$. In order to obtain the equations satisfied by the solution of the basic problem, the Lagrangian associated with minimization under the constrained (11) is introduced. We can easily show that the stress field sought $\underline{\sigma}$ can be expressed in terms of a displacement field \underline{v} :

$$\underline{\sigma} = \underline{\sigma}(\underline{v}), \text{ with } \underline{\sigma}(\underline{v}) = C : \underline{\varepsilon}(\underline{v}) \quad (12)$$

It means that the basic problem is rewritten in terms of displacement and becomes:

Find, for a given $\underline{\theta}$,

$$\min_{(\underline{u}, \underline{v}) \in H^1(\Omega)^2, \underline{\sigma}(\underline{v}) \in \mathcal{S}_{Ad}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}, \underline{\sigma}(\underline{v}), \underline{\theta}) \quad (13)$$

A finite element formulation of the basic problem is proposed.

- Then, defining the cost function: $\mathcal{G}(\underline{\theta}) = \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}(\underline{\theta}), \underline{\sigma}(\underline{\theta}), \underline{\theta})$, the identification of $\underline{\theta}$ is performed as the minimization of $\mathcal{G}(\underline{\theta})$:

$$\underline{\theta}^{opt} = \text{Arg min}_{\underline{\theta}} \mathcal{G}(\underline{\theta}) = \text{Arg min}_{\underline{\theta}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}(\underline{\theta}), \underline{\sigma}(\underline{\theta}), \underline{\theta}) \quad (14)$$

3. MULTI-SCALE IDENTIFICATION STRATEGY

3.1 Framework: direct problem and measurements

For the multi-scale approach, the identification framework is the one of a mechanical test on a specimen Ω_M where the force edge $\partial_f \Omega$ is measured as well as the displacement field on one sub-part of the specimen surface Ω_m (Figure 2). We can also assume a part of the edge of the specimen to be free of load $\partial_d \Omega$ and we have no idea on the boundary condition on $\partial_\theta \Omega$. The elastic properties of the specimen collected in the vector $\underline{\theta}^M$ are sought as homogeneous isotropic, and the ones of the measurement part collected in the vector $\underline{\theta}^m$ are sought as heterogeneous isotropic. The boundary conditions are only known on the macro fields and displacement is only measured on the micro fields. This can lead to the following model and equations describing the available information, both experimental and theoretical. The equations verified by the macro stress $\underline{\sigma}^M$, the macro displacement \underline{u}^M , the macro parameter $\underline{\theta}^M$, the micro stress $\underline{\sigma}^m$, the micro displacement \underline{u}^m and the micro parameter $\underline{\theta}^m$ are as follow:

- On Ω_M ,

Figure 2 - Multi-scale: direct problem

- Equilibrium: $\underline{\underline{div}} \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M = \underline{\underline{0}}$
 - Constitutive relation: $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M = \underline{\underline{C}}(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M) \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^M$
 - Kinematic compatibility: $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^M = \underline{\underline{\nabla}}^s \underline{\underline{u}}^M$
 - On Ω_m ,
 - Equilibrium: $\underline{\underline{div}} \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m = \underline{\underline{0}}$
 - Constitutive relation: $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m = \underline{\underline{C}}(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^m$
 - Kinematic compatibility: $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^m = \underline{\underline{\nabla}}^s \underline{\underline{u}}^m$
 - Displacement measurement: $\underline{\underline{u}}^m = \underline{\underline{\tilde{u}}}$
 - On $\partial_d\Omega$,
 - Free edge boundary condition: $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M \cdot \underline{\underline{n}} = \underline{\underline{0}}$
 - On $\partial_f\Omega$,
 - Measured traction boundary condition: $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M \cdot \underline{\underline{n}} = \underline{\underline{f}}$
- or,
- Measured global load: $\int_{\partial\Omega_f} \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M \cdot \underline{\underline{n}} dS \cdot \underline{\underline{N}}_0 = F_0$
- On $\partial_\theta\Omega = \partial\Omega \setminus \partial_d\Omega \setminus \partial_f\Omega$, no boundary condition

3.2 Splitting of the equations: macro fields and micro fields

As for the mono-scale approach, the various equations of the identification problem are split into two groups like Table 2:

	Macro fields Ω_M	Micro fields Ω_m
Reliable	$\underline{\underline{div}} \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M = \underline{\underline{0}}$ $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^M = \underline{\underline{\nabla}}^s \underline{\underline{u}}^M$ $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M \cdot \underline{\underline{n}} = \underline{\underline{0}}$ $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M \cdot \underline{\underline{n}} = \underline{\underline{f}}$, or $\int_{\partial\Omega_f} \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M \cdot \underline{\underline{n}} dS \cdot \underline{\underline{N}}_0 = F_0$	$\underline{\underline{div}} \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m = \underline{\underline{0}}$ $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^m = \underline{\underline{\nabla}}^s \underline{\underline{u}}^m$
Less reliable	$\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M = \underline{\underline{C}}(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M) \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^M$	$\underline{\underline{u}}^m = \underline{\underline{\tilde{u}}}$ $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m = \underline{\underline{C}}(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^m$

Table 2 - Different groups of multi-scale equations

We can also easily show that the stress field sought $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M$ and $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m$ can be expressed in terms of a displacement field $\underline{\underline{v}}^M$ and $\underline{\underline{v}}^m$:

$$\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M = \underline{\underline{\sigma}}(\underline{\underline{v}}^M), \text{ with } \underline{\underline{\sigma}}(\underline{\underline{v}}^M) = \underline{\underline{C}} : \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}(\underline{\underline{v}}^M) \quad (15)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m = \underline{\underline{\sigma}}(\underline{\underline{v}}^m), \text{ with } \underline{\underline{\sigma}}(\underline{\underline{v}}^m) = \underline{\underline{C}} : \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}(\underline{\underline{v}}^m) \quad (16)$$

3.3 Coupling between macro fields and micro fields

A key point of the multi-scale approach is to combine and transfer the information of displacement and stress efficiently between the macro fields and micro fields. For the displacement fields, the first try is based on Diffuse Approximation (DA). The DA has been initially developed to generate smooth approximation functions known at given sets of points [10] in the early 1990s. The basic idea of the diffuse approximation is to replace the "finite element approximation" interpolation, which valid on an element, by a local weighted least squares fitting, which is valid in a small neighbourhood of a point. Later, it has been widely used in different fields, such as optimization through response surfaces [11], field transfer in non linear inelastic analysis [12] and reconstructing the gradients of noisy full-field data [13]. In our case, every macro node in the measured domain Ω_m has a neighbourhood of some micro nodes. On other words, the displacement of such macro nodes could be reconstructed by the neighbourhood micro nodes with the diffuse approximation. For the stress fields, we make the assumption of global load of the micro field by accumulating the stress information of the macros nodes on the boundary between micro and macro fields. Here, we express simply the coupling operators by the following equations:

$$C_u(\underline{u}^M, \underline{u}^m) = 0 \quad (17)$$

$$C_v(\underline{v}^M, \underline{v}^m) = 0 \quad (18)$$

3.4 The multi-scale identification problem

In order to identify the properties of the material, $(\underline{u}^M, \underline{\sigma}^M, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\sigma}^m, \underline{\theta}^M, \underline{\theta}^m)$ are sought as the solution of a minimization problem where the reliable equations are considered as constraints and the less reliable equations are defined a function that is to be minimized. Here we take the case of reliable traction distribution as an example to explain in detail. We introduce:

- the space associated with the constraints on macro displacement:

$$\mathcal{U}_{Ad}^M = \{\underline{u}^M \in H^1(\Omega_M)\} \quad (19)$$

- the space associated with the constraints on micro displacement:

$$\mathcal{U}_{Ad}^m = \{\underline{u}^m \in H^1(\Omega_m)\} \quad (20)$$

- the space associated with the constraints on macro stress:

- equilibrium and free edge:

$$\mathcal{S}_{Ad}^{0M} = \{\underline{\sigma}^M \in H_{div}(\Omega_M) / \underline{div} \underline{\sigma}^M = \underline{0} \text{ sur } \Omega_M, \underline{\sigma}^M \cdot \underline{n} = \underline{0} \text{ sur } \partial_d \Omega\} \quad (21)$$

- traction distribution on $\partial_f \Omega$:

$$\mathcal{S}_{Ad}^{fM} = \{\underline{\sigma}^M \in H_{div}^f(\Omega_M) / \underline{\sigma}^M \cdot \underline{n} = \underline{f} \text{ sur } \partial_f \Omega\} \quad (22)$$

- the space associated with the constraints on micro stress:

$$\mathcal{S}_{Ad}^{0m} = \{\underline{\sigma}^m \in H_{div}(\Omega_m) / \underline{div} \underline{\sigma}^m = \underline{0} \text{ sur } \Omega_m\} \quad (23)$$

- the term of distance of the macro constitutive relation:

$$\mathcal{J}_1(\underline{\sigma}^M, \underline{u}^M, \underline{\theta}^M) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_M} (\underline{\sigma}^M - C^M \underline{\xi}(\underline{u}^M)) C^{M-1} (\underline{\sigma}^M - C^M \underline{\xi}(\underline{u}^M)) d\Omega_M \quad (24)$$

- the term of distance of the micro constitutive relation:

$$\mathcal{J}_2(\underline{\sigma}^m, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\theta}^m) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_m} (\underline{\sigma}^m - C^m \underline{\xi}(\underline{u}^m)) C^{m-1} (\underline{\sigma}^m - C^m \underline{\xi}(\underline{u}^m)) d\Omega_m \quad (25)$$

- the term of the distance of displacement measurements on Ω_m :

$$\mathcal{J}_3(\underline{u}^m) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_m} \|\underline{u}^m - \underline{\tilde{u}}\|^2 d\Omega_m \quad (26)$$

- the term of the distance of displacement coupling on Ω_m :

$$\mathcal{J}_4(\underline{u}^M, \underline{u}^m) = \frac{1}{2} C_u^2 \quad (27)$$

- the term of the distance of stress coupling on Ω_m :

$$\mathcal{J}_5(\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m) = \frac{1}{2} C_v^2 \quad (28)$$

We can conclude the definition of the identification problem as the following:

Find the field $(\underline{u}^M, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m) \in \mathcal{U}_{Ad} \times \mathcal{S}_{Ad}$
and the set of parameters $(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m)$:

$$\min_{(\underline{u}^M, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \in \mathcal{U}_{Ad} \times \mathcal{S}_{Ad} \times \Theta_{Ad}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}^M, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \quad (29)$$

where $\mathcal{U}_{Ad} = \mathcal{U}_{Ad}^M \cap \mathcal{U}_{Ad}^m$, $\mathcal{S}_{Ad} = \mathcal{S}_{Ad}^{0M} \cap \mathcal{S}_{Ad}^{fM} \cap \mathcal{S}_{Ad}^{0m}$,
and $\mathcal{J} = \mathcal{J}_1 + \mathcal{J}_2 + \alpha \mathcal{J}_3 + \gamma \mathcal{J}_4 + \beta \mathcal{J}_5$.

In practice, the minimization is split into a sequential minimization:

$$\min_{(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \in \Theta_{Ad}} \min_{(\underline{u}^M, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m) \in \mathcal{U}_{Ad} \times \mathcal{S}_{Ad}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}^M, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \quad (30)$$

- For a given $(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m)$, find $(\underline{u}^M, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m)$ minimizing $\mathcal{J}(\underline{u}^M, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m)$ under the above constraints. This is the basic problem:

$$\min_{(\underline{u}^M, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m) \in \mathcal{U}_{Ad} \times \mathcal{S}_{Ad}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}^M, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M, \underline{u}^m, \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \quad (31)$$

- Then, defining: $\mathcal{G}(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) = \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}^M(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M), \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M), \underline{u}^m(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^m), \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^m), \underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m)$, the identification of $(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m)$ is performed as the minimization of $\mathcal{G}(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m)$:

$$\begin{aligned} (\underline{\underline{\theta}}^{optM}, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^{optm}) &= \text{Arg} \min_{(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \in \Theta_{Ad}} \mathcal{G}(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \\ &= \text{Arg} \min_{(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \in \Theta_{Ad}} \mathcal{J}(\underline{u}^M(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M), \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^M(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^M), \underline{u}^m(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^m), \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^m(\underline{\underline{\theta}}^m), \underline{\underline{\theta}}^M, \underline{\underline{\theta}}^m) \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

4. APPLICATION ON NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

4.1 Mono-scale identification

In this section, we propose the illustration of the method on a numerical example based on the study of the elastic properties of a plate with three inclusion. A calculation is performed representing a tensile test on a whole plate as sketched in Figure 3(a), with reference values of the heterogeneous and isotropic material parameters. The displacements obtained from this calculation are transferred on a regular grid representing the DIC measurement grid and are illustrated on Figures 3(b).

The plate is assumed to be isotropic and heterogeneous for this illustrating example. The behaviour is thus described by the Lamé coefficients: matrix (λ_1, μ_1) and inclusions $(\lambda_2, \mu_2), (\lambda_3, \mu_3), (\lambda_4, \mu_4)$.

Figure 3 - Numerical example of a plate with three inclusions: reference calculation and simulated displacement exact measurement

Figure 4 - Comparison of reliable traction distribution and reliable global load

4.1.1 Comparison of different boundary conditions

In order to compare the boundary condition of traction distribution and global load, we reform the identification on part A whose boundary is close to inclusion 2 so that the force distribution on boundary τ_{AB} is affected by the inclusion, but only the global load on τ_{AB} is supposed to be known. In the case of reliable global load, it is assumed that there is a force on the middle point of τ_{AB} . However, it needs a hypothesis of distribution in the case of reliable traction distribution. So we assume that the traction distribution on τ_{AB} is constant, as the blue curve in Figure 4(a), but in fact the exact stress distribution is like the green curve.

Figure 4(b) presents the identification result of parameters for the various boundary condition formulation. The results are significantly better by presuming the force condition as a global load (the red groups: the mean value of the ratio of identified parameter and reference almost equal to 1). Moreover, we can find that identification relative error on the part near the false assumption boundary is the greatest (the blue groups of $\lambda_2=34.78\%$ and $\mu_2=10.3\%$). It means that the model error on the traction distribution would lead to wrong identification result.

4.1.2 Optimizing the weighting coefficient

From the above example, we find that the model error of traction distribution can lead to erroneous results. In order to decrease this model error and restore the balance, we put the equation of forced boundary into the minimization functional. It means that we use the case of less reliable traction distribution. A key point is optimizing the weighting coefficient β of the distance to traction distribution.

Firstly, we determine $\beta_0 = \frac{U_{ref} K U_{ref}}{F^T * F}$, $\beta = \beta_0 * 10^\gamma$. Then we change γ from -9 to 8 and solve the identification problem independently. Figure 5 shows the influence of the weighting coefficient β on the identification result of λ and μ . We can divide the results into three groups:

- $-9 \leq \gamma < -6$: $\theta_{id} \neq \theta_{ref}$, $\frac{\theta_{id}^k}{\theta_{ref}^k} = 0.8657(\text{constant})$

- $-6 \leq \gamma < -2$: $\theta_{id} \approx \theta_{ref}$
- $\gamma \geq -2$: $\theta_{id} \neq \theta_{ref}$, $\frac{\theta_{id}^k}{\theta_{ref}^k} \neq constant$

(a) Identification result of λ .

(b) Identification result of μ .

Figure 5 - Comparison of influence of weighting coefficient β on the identification result

(a) Calculated traction distribution from the identification result of different β

(b) L-curve of $J_1 + \alpha J_2$ and J_3

Figure 6 - Comparison of influence of weighting coefficient β on stress distribution and objective function

In order to find out the reason, on one hand, we calculate and compare the stress on the boundary τ_{AB} from the result. From Figure 6(a) we find that:

- when $\gamma = -8$, the stress distribution (the blue line) has the same shape of the exact distribution, but with a constant distance. We can conclude that too small β means weak influence of force information, so the identification result has good ratio between parameters, but loses the global stiffness;
- when $\gamma = -4$, the stress distribution (the magenta line) is the closest curve to the exact stress distribution and still has the same shape;
- when $\gamma = -2.62, -2.21, -2$, the influence of force information continue to increase, so the stress distribution leaves from the exact distribution to the false assumption;
- If $\gamma > 0$, the stress distribution will approximate the false assumption of distribution, leading to identification results similar to the case with reliable traction distribution.

On the other hand, the L-curve was also used to compare different terms of objective function in order to find out the optimal weighting coefficient. Figure 6(b) shows that $\gamma = -2.62$ is the compromise point where both values of $J_1 + \alpha J_2$ and J_3 are reasonable.

Figure 7(a) presents that adding the function of traction distribution with reasonable weighting coefficient (two groups of less reliable traction distribution) improves significantly the identification results. Since defining $\gamma = -4$

can correct the model error of the traction distribution, the parameter of inclusion 2 (near τ_{AB}) are the best in the magenta group. However, it reduces the global rigidity: all the ratio of parameters are below 1. In contrast, due to the global compromise of objective function, when $\gamma = -2.62$ (the green group) the parameter of global matrix and inclusion 4 (far from τ_{AB}) are best. We can conclude that the model error of traction distribution could be reduced by optimizing the weighting coefficient and restore the balance between strain and displacement.

Figure 7 - Comparison of different reliability of information

4.1.3 Influence of measurement perturbation

In order to compare the influence of measurement noise, we use the same example of a plate with three inclusions (Figure 3), and consider two case: the global load on the boundary is reliable or not. We add 5% noise on both displacement measurement and force measurement. The result are compared in terms of $\frac{\theta_k}{\theta_1} / \frac{\theta_{kref}}{\theta_{1ref}}$ to compensate the fact that perturbation on the load lead to an erroneous global rigidity. Figure 7(b) shows that both two formulations (reliable or less reliable global load) can obtain a reasonable identification result, but the influence of noise is greater in the case assuming less reliable global load.

4.2 Multi-scale identification

4.2.1 Identification of macro properties

Figure 8 - Numerical example of a plate: reference calculation and simulated displacement exact measurement

In order to validate the approach of multi-scale identification, the first step is only identifying the macro properties of sample. The calculation is performed representing a tensile test on a plate as sketched in Figure 8(a), with

reference values of local composition parameters (blue composition: λ_1, μ_1 and red composition: λ_2, μ_2) under assumption of plane stress. The displacements obtained from this calculation are transferred on a regular grid representing the DIC measurement grid and are illustrated on Figures 8(b). Some noise can be added to these exact fields in order to represent the measurement perturbations. The magnitude of the additive noise is given in percent of the mean value of the displacements or the mean value of the force measurement.

Plate	λ_{m1}	λ_{m2}	μ_{m1}	μ_{m2}	λ_M	μ_M
Homogeneous	1	1	0.5	0.5	1	0.5
Heterogeneous	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.8482	0.6473

Table 3 - Identification results of macro properties of homogeneous plate and heterogeneous plate

Table 3 presents the identification result of a plate where the micro properties in the measurement zone are known and the macro properties of the whole sample are identified. In the homogeneous case, the identified macro properties are the same as the micro ones. In the heterogeneous case, the identified macro properties are between the two values of micro properties. Moreover, the identified properties are very close to those obtained by numerical homogenization: $\lambda_M^H = 0.8483$, $\mu_M^H = 0.6476$.

4.2.2 Identification of macro and micro properties

The second step to validate the approach of multi-scale identification is identifying both the macro and micro properties. We carry out the calculation on the same sample (Figure 8(a)), and in the heterogeneous case. In the part of macro identification, we find $\lambda_M = 0.8483$ and $\mu_M = 0.6472$, which are validated based on numerical homogenization. Figure 9(a) shows the local strain energy error of identified macro properties. The error focus on the corner of the plate. In the part of micro identification, the developing of minimisation algorithm is in progress. The local strain energy error of reference micro properties is shown on Figure 9(b). We can find that error distributes on the whole plate, but it is not important. Full multi-scale identification is currently under progress and should be presented at ICCM20.

Figure 9 - Local strain energy error

5. CONCLUSION

We proposed an identification strategy dedicated to full-field displacement measurements based on the modified constitutive relation error. Its key point is to construct a trade-off between all the available information, both experimental and theoretical. On the illustrating example, it was shown that the method allows the calculation with different kinds of boundary conditions and how to balance between the various possible experimental informations so that the inverse problem is well-posed. We also propose a two-scale approach where heterogeneous properties are sought at the measurement level and homogeneous ones at the specimen/structure level. Different coupling schemes are proposed which can combine the stress and displacement fields at both the micro and macro scales. As the mono-scale approach, the equations are split according to the reliability of information and here the coupling equation is considered as less reliable. A first step towards multi-scale identification has been made and should be completed by the study of the identification of all properties.

REFERENCE

1. Lucas B.D., Kanade T. (1981) An iterative image registration technique with an application to stereo vision. *Proceedings of the 7th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, IJCAI'81* vol.2, San Francisco, CA, USA, 674-679
2. Burt P.J., Yen C., Xu X. (1982) Local correlation measures for motion analysis: a comparative study. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Pattern Recognition and Image Processing* Las Vegas, NV, USA, 269-274
3. Sutton M.A., Wolters W.J., Peters W.H., Ranson W.F., McNeill S.R. (1983) Determination of displacements using an improved digital correlation method. *Image and Vision Computing* vol.1, no.3, 133-139
4. Avril S., Bonnet M., Bretelle A.S. and others (2008) Overview of identification methods of mechanical parameters based on full-field measurements. *Experimental Mechanics* 48-4, 381-402
5. Collins J., Hart G., Kennedy B. (1974) Statistical identification of structures. *AIAA Journal* vol. 12, no.2, 185-190
6. Ladevèze P., Leguillon D. (1983) Error estimate procedure in the finite element method and applications. *SIAM Journal on Numerical Analysis* vol. 20, 485-509
7. Ben Azzouna M., Feissel P. and Villon P. (2012) Modified Constitutive Relation Error Strategy for Elastic Properties Identification. *10^e SEM XII International Congress on Experimental and Applied Mechanics*, Costa Mesa, CA, USA
8. Feissel P. and Allix O. (2007) An identification strategy based on the modified constitutive relation error for transient dynamics with corrupted data: the elastic case. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 196:13-164, 1968-1983
9. Deraemaeker A. Ladevèze P. and Leguillon D. (2002) Reduced bases for model updating in structural dynamics based on constitutive relation error. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* vol.191, 2427-2444
10. B. Nayroles, G.Touzot, and P.Villon. (1992) Generalizing the finite element method: Diffuse approximation and diffuse elements. *Computational Mechanics*, 10, 307-318.
11. P. Breitkopf, H. Naceur, A. Rassineux, and P. Villon. (2005) Moving least squares response surface approximation: formulation and metal forming applications. *Computers and Structures*, 83 (17-18):1411-1428.
12. D. Brancherie, P.Villon, and A. Ibrahimbegovic. (2007) On a consistent field transfer in non linear inelastic analysis and ultimate load computation. *Computational Mechanics*, page online.
13. S. Avril, P. Feissel, F. Pierron, and P. Villon. (2010) Comparison of two approaches for differentiating full-field data in solid mechanics. *Measurement Science & Technology*, 21(1), pp.015703.